

Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Related Impurities of Cilnidipine and Chlorthalidone in Tablet Dosage Form by RP-HPLC

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Abstract

A novel HPLC method was developed and validated for the estimation of related impurities of cilnidipine and chlorthalidone in pharmaceutical formulations. The chromatographic separation was carried out by isocratic elution using an Hypersil BDS C18 column (250×4.6mm; 5 μ). The mobile phase was composed of phosphate buffer at a pH of 4.0 and acetonitrile in the ratio of 80:20 (V/V) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The eluents were detected and quantified at a UV detection wavelength of 225 nm. Calibration curves of all analytes in the range of 1-15 μ g/mL showed a good correlation linearly ($r \geq 0.99$) with recovery rate of more than 98% for each analyte. The percentage RSD in intraday, interday precision and ruggedness were found to be less than 5. Small variations in the developed conditions like mobile phase ratio, flow rate, pH and UV wavelength do not influence the results. The detailed quantitative results of this study show that this method is simple, quick, precise, accurate, sensitive, cost-effective and robust. Thus, the method development and validation result confirm that this method be successfully applied for determination and quantification of impurities for the routine quality control analysis in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Keywords: Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Related Substances, Impurity, Rp-HPLC

1. Introduction

Chlorthalidone is chemically 2-Chloro-5-(1-hydroxy-3-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-isoindol-1-yl)benzene-1-sulfonamide and it is in the sulfamoyl benzamide class. As it lacks the benzothiadiazine structure of the thiazide-type diuretics, it is called a thiazide-like diuretic [1]. Chlorthalidone is freely soluble in dimethylacetamide (DMA), dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), and methanol; it is also soluble in warm ethanol [2].

Cilnidipine is chemically 3-(*E*)-3-Phenyl-2-propenyl 5-(2-methoxyethyl) 2,6-dimethyl-4-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate and it is a calcium channel blocker, calcium antagonist accompanied with L-type and N-type calcium channel blocking functions [3].

Literatures available on various UV methods are reported in the literature for the estimation of Cilnidipine and Chlorthalidone individually and in-combination with other drugs [4] and on various RP-HPLC methods are reported [5-7]. According to literature survey there is no official method for the simultaneous estimation of related impurities for Chlorthalidone and Cilnidipine by RP-HPLC in pharmaceutical dosage forms. In this study, an HPLC method

was optimized and validated for simultaneous estimation and validation of related impurities in pharmaceutical dosage forms in accordance with the ICH guidelines [8, 9].

2. Materials and Methods

Chemicals & Reagents used: Cilnidipine, Chlorthalidone, Water and Methanol for HPLC, Acetonitrile for HPLC.

Instruments and Chromatographic Conditions: LC-10AT HPLC system was used for method development, degradation studies and validation. Data acquisition was performed on Spinchrom HPLC software. The separation were achieved on C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) column. The column was maintained at room temperature and the eluent was monitored at 222 nm using UV detector. The mixture of Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer 0.05M (pH 4.0): Acetonitrile (80:20 v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min was used as a mobile phase. The injection volume was 20 μ l.

Preparation of standard solutions

Chlorthalidone standard stock solution: (1000 μ g/mL)

A 100 mg of Chlorthalidone was weighed and transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with methanol.

Cilnidipine standard stock solution: (1000 μ g/mL)

A 100 mg of Cilnidipine was weighed and transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with methanol.

Impurity-1 Standard stock solution: (1000 μ g/mL)

A 10 mg of Impurity-1 was weighed and transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with methanol.

Impurity-2 Standard stock solution: (1000 μ g/mL)

A 10 mg of Impurity-2 was weighed and transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with methanol.

Preparation of standard solution of mixtures of Chlorthalidone and Cilnidipine (10 μ g/mL)

Take 1 mL from the Chlorthalidone stock solution and 1mL from Cilnidipine stock solution and transferred to 10 mL volumetric flask and volume made up to the mark by mobile phase.

Preparation of Combine standard solution of Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 (10 μ g/mL)

Take 1 mL from the Impurity-1 stock solution and 1mL from the Impurity-2 stock solution and transferred to 10 mL volumetric flask and volume made up to the mark by mobile phase.

Preparation of Mobile phase

Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer 0.05M (pH 4.0): Acetonitrile (80:20: v/v)

Preparation of sample solution (Chlorthalidone 1000 μ g/mL)

Weigh and powdered 10 tablets. Take tablet powder equivalent to 100mg of Chlorthalidone into a 100ml volumetric flask. Add 60ml mobile phase and shake for 10 minutes and sonicate for 5mins. Make up volume with mobile phase. Filter the solution with Whatman filter paper no-1 and first few drops of filtrate were discarded. The solution was injected 20 μ l. The areas of resulting peak were measured at 225 nm.

3. Validation of RP-HPLC Method

1) Linearity

The linearity for Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 were assessed by analysis of combined standard solution in range of 5-15 µg/ml respectively 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25, 1.5 ml solutions were pipette out from the Stock solution of Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 and transfer to 100 ml volumetric flask and make up with mobile phase to obtain 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5 and 15 µg/ml, respectively.

In term of slope, intercept and correlation co-efficient value. The graph of peak area obtained verses respective concentration was plotted.

2) Precision

Results should be expressed as Relative standard deviation (RSD) or coefficient of variance.

a) Repeatability

Standard solution containing Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 (10 µg/mL) was injected six times and areas of peaks were measured and % R.S.D. was calculated.

b) Intra-day precision

Standard solution containing Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 (10 µg/mL) were analyzed three times on the same day and % R.S.D was calculated.

c) Inter-day precision

Standard solution containing Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 (10 µg/mL) were analyzed three times on the different day and % R.S.D was calculated.

3) Accuracy

For Impurity -1 and Impurity-2 (10 µg/mL) drug solution was taken in three different flask label A, B and C. Spiked 80%, 100%, 120% of standard solution in it and diluted up to 10ml. The area of each solution peak was measured at 225 nm. The amount of Impurity -1 and Impurity-2 was calculated at each level and % recoveries were computed.

4) LOD and LOQ

The LOD was estimated from the set of 3 calibration curves used to determination method linearity. The LOD may be calculated as,

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times (\text{SD}/\text{Slope})$$

Where,

SD= Standard deviation of Y-intercepts of 3 calibration curves.

Slope = Mean slope of the 3 calibration curves.

The LOQ was estimated from the set of 3 calibration curves used to determine method linearity. The LOQ may be calculated as,

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times (\text{SD}/\text{Slope})$$

Where,

SD = Standard deviation of Y-intercepts of 3 calibration curves.

Slope = Mean slope of the 3 calibration curves.

5) Robustness

Following parameters were changed one by one and their effect was observed on system suitability for standard preparation.

1. Flow rate of mobile phase was changed (± 0.2 ml/min) 0.8 ml/min and 1.2 ml/min.

2. pH of Mobile phase was changed (± 0.2) 3.8 and 4.2.

3. Ratio of Mobile phase was changed (± 2) Buffer: Acetonitrile (82:18) and Buffer: Acetonitrile (78:22)

4. Result and Discussion

Specificity

Figure 1: Chromatogram of Cilnidipine and Chlorthalidone standard

Figure 2: Chromatogram of Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 standard

Figure 3: Chromatogram of Cilnidipine and Chlorthalidone sample in drug

Figure 4: Chromatogram of drug Blank

The Chromatograms of Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 standard and Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 sample show no interference with the Chromatogram of Chlorthalidone, Cilnidipine, Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 Blank, so the developed method is Specific.

Linearity and Range

The linearity for Cilnidipine, Chlorthalidone drug, impurity-1 and impurity-2 were performed by analysis of standard solution combined in range of 5-15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ drug concentration respectively. The Correlation co-efficient value for all drug components of linearity curve was achieved as 0.99. Regression line equation for Cilnidipine drug and Chlorthalidone drug and impurity-1 and impurity-2 components are as following:

For Cilnidipine drug: $y = 44.79x + 44.3$ and for Chlorthalidone drug: $y = 23.38x + 10.83$ and for impurity-1 $y = 19.13x + 17.60$, for impurity-2 $y = 14.59x + 12.88$

Table 1: Linearity data for Cilnidipine drug

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak Area
1	1	69.508
2	5	198.885
3	7.5	289.558
4	10	396.117
5	12.5	487.404
6	15	591.841

Table 2: Linearity data for Chlorthalidone drug

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak Area
1	1	41.351
2	5	122.982
3	7.5	179.267
4	10	245.324
5	12.5	302.072
6	15	366.765

Table 3: Linearity data for impurity-1

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak Area
1	0.25	31.761
2	5	104.375
3	7.5	155.239
4	10	207.427
5	12.5	258.03
6	15	310.493

Table 4: Linearity data for impurity-2

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak Area
1	0.25	23.784
2	5	78.995
3	7.5	117.741
4	10	157.557
5	12.5	196.245
	15	236.321

Figure 5: Overlay chromatogram for mixture of different concentrations for Cilnidipine and Chlorthalidone drugs

Figure 7: Calibration Curve of Chlorthalidone drug (1-15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Figure 8: Calibration Curve of impurity-1 (0.25-15µg/ml)

Figure 9: Calibration Curve of impurity-2 (0.25-15µg/ml)

5. Precision

i. Repeatability

Repeatability data of peak area for Cilnidipine, Chlorthalidone drug, impurity-1 and impurity-2, basis on six measurements of same solution of Cilnidipine, Chlorthalidone drug, impurity-1 and impurity-2 are depicted in table. The % RSD for Cilnidipine, Chlorthalidone drug, impurity-1 and impurity-2 components were found to be 1.62, 1.48, 1.72 and 1.51 respectively.

Table 5: Repeatability data for Cilnidipine drug

Cilnidipine drug				
S. No.	Conc (µg/ml)	Peak Area	Mean ± SD	% R.S.D
1.	10	403.247	391.83 ±6.34	1.62
		390.212		
		385.905		
		391.394		
		393.746		
		386.457		

Table 6: Repeatability data for Chlorthalidone drug

Chlorthalidone drug				
S. No.	Conc (µg/ml)	Peak Area	Mean ± SD	% R.S.D
1.	10	249.749	243.50 ±3.60	1.48
		241.636		
		238.993		
		242.377		
		243.866		
		244.362		

Table 7: Repeatability data for impurity-1

Impurity-1				
S. No.	Conc (µg/ml)	Peak Area	Mean ± SD	% R.S.D
1.	10	204.334	205.80 ±3.53	1.72
		203.096		
		205.773		
		211.156		
		208.675		
		201.793		

Table 8: Repeatability data for impurity-2

Impurity-2				
S. No.	Conc (µg/ml)	Peak Area	Mean ± SD	% R.S.D
1.	10	155.214	156.59 ±2.37	1.51
		154.283		
		156.286		
		160.377		
		158.497		
		154.914		

ii. Intraday precision

The results of intraday precision for Cilnidipine and Chlorthalidone drug impurity-1 and impurity-2 components are shown in below table. % R.S.D. for Intraday precision was found to be 1.30-3.35 for Cilnidipine drug and 1.03-2.72 for Chlorthalidone drug and 1.58-2.88 for impurity-1 and 2.46-4.38 for impurity-2.

Table 9: Intraday precision data for estimation of Cilnidipine drug

Cilnidipine drug			
S. No.	Concen. (µg/ml)	Mean peak area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
1	0.25	67.92± 2.28	3.35
2	10	395.86± 5.64	1.42
3	15	582.48± 7.60	1.30

Table 10: Intraday precision data for estimation of Chlorthalidone drug

Chlorthalidone drug			
S. No.	Concen. (µg/ml)	Mean peak area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
1	0	40.34± 1.10	2.72
2	10	245.41± 3.92	1.60
3	15	361.53± 3.83	1.06

Table 11: Intraday precision data for estimation of impurity-1

Impurity-1			
S. No.	Concen. (µg/ml)	Mean peak area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
1	2.5	31.41± 0.90	2.88
2	10	205.11± 5.96	2.91
3	12.5	307.10 ± 4.86	1.58

Table 12: Intraday precision data for estimation of impurity-2

Impurity-2			
S. No.	Concen. (µg/ml)	Mean peak area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
1	2.5	23.22± 1.02	4.38
2	10	156.27± 3.85	2.46
3	12.5	232.37± 5.72	2.46

iii. Interday precision

The results for intraday precision for Cilnidipine and Chlorthalidone drug impurity-1 and impurity-2 are shown in table. % R.S.D for interday precision was found to be 0.236-0.978 for Cilnidipine drug and 0.198-0.805 for Chlorthalidone drug and for impurity-1 and for impurity-2 0.384-1.029 for impurity-2.

Table 13: Interday precision results for estimation of Cilnidipine drug

Cilnidipine drug			
S. No.	Concen. (µg/ml)	Mean peak area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
1	0.25	68.34± 0.94	1.37
2	10	385.01±5.45	1.42
3	15	586.73±6.32	1.08

Table 14: Interday precision results for estimation of Chlorthalidone drug

Chlorthalidone drug			
S. No.	Concen. (µg/ml)	Mean peak area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
1	0	41.22± 1.04	2.52
2	10	241.33± 1.95	0.81
3	15	365.42 ± 6.98	1.91

Table 15: Interday precision results for estimation of Impurity-1

Impurity-1			
S. No.	Concen. (µg/ml)	Mean peak area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
1	2.5	31.57 ± 0.77	2.44
2	10	205.57 ± 3.20	1.56
3	12.5	308.33 ± 4.18	1.36

Table 16: Interday precision results for estimation of Impurity-2

Impurity-2			
S. No.	Concen. (µg/ml)	Mean peak area ± SD (n=3)	% RSD
1	2.5	22.87 ± 0.35	1.51
2	10	155.15 ± 1.20	0.77
3	12.5	232.88 ± 1.42	0.61

6. Accuracy

The recovery study was carried out at three level of 80%, 100% and 120% of target drug concentration. Percentage recovery for impurity-1 and impurity-2 was found to be

Table 17: Recovery data for impurity-1

S. NO.	Recovery Level	Sample amount (µg/ml)	Drug Added (µg/ml)	Drug recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	% Average Recovery ± SD
1	80 %	10	8	8.032	100.40	99.99 ± 1.66
2		10	8	7.853	98.16	
3		10	8	8.112	101.40	
4		10	10	9.898	98.98	
5	100 %	10	10	10.269	102.69	100.95 ± 1.85
6		10	10	10.118	101.18	
7		10	12	11.923	99.36	
8	120 %	10	12	12.228	101.90	101.36 ± 1.77
9		10	12	12.338	102.82	

Table 18: Recovery data for impurity-2

S. NO.	Recovery Level	Sample Amount	Amount Added	Amount recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	% Average Recovery ±SD
1	80 %	10	8	8.123	101.54	101.01 ± 2.94
2		10	8	8.306	103.82	
3		10	8	7.834	97.93	
4		10	10	10.294	102.94	
5	100 %	10	10	9.875	98.75	99.78 ± 2.80
6		10	10	9.763	97.63	
7		10	12	12.201	101.68	
8	120 %	10	12	11.877	98.98	100.25 ± 1.35
9		10	12	12.012	100.10	

7. LOD and LOQ

Calibration curve is repeated for five times and the standard deviation (SD) of intercepts was computed. Then the LOD and LOQ value were calculated as follows: $LOD = 3.3 * SD/slope$ value of calibration curve.

$LOQ = 10 * SD/slope$ value of calibration curve.

Where, SD = Standard deviation (SD) of intercepts.

Table 19: Limit of Detection results for Cilnidipine drug and Chlorthalidone impurity-1 and impurity-2

Cilnidipine drug	Chlorthalidone drug	Impurity-1	Impurity-2
LOD	LOD	LOD	LOD
= $3.3 * (SD / Slope)$			
= $3.3 * (4.553/39.350)$	= $3.3 * (2.782/24.415)$	= $3.3 * (0.514/20.601)$	= $3.3 * (0.406/15.726)$
0.382 μ g/ml	= 0.376 μ g/ml	= 0.082 μ g/ml	= 0.085 μ g/ml

Table 20: Limit of Quantitation results for Cilnidipine drug and Chlorthalidone impurity-1 and impurity-2

Cilnidipine drug	Chlorthalidone drug	Impurity-1	Impurity-2
LOQ	LOQ	LOQ	LOQ
= $10 * (SD / Slope)$			
= $10 * (4.553/39.350)$	= $10 * (2.782/24.415)$	= $10 * (0.514/20.601)$	= $10 * (0.406/15.726)$
= 1.157 μ g/ml	= 1.139 μ g/ml	= 0.249 μ g/ml	= 0.258 μ g/ml

8. Robustness

The effect of chromatographic parameters modifications was found to be within the limit as mentioned in the below table. The value of % RSD were found to be less than 2.0%.

Table 21: Robustness data for Cilnidipine drug

S. No.	Flow rate (-0.2 ml/minute) Area	Flow rate (0.2ml/minute) Area	pH (-0.2) Area	pH (+0.2) Area	Mobile phase (- 2) Area	Mobile phase (+2) Area
1	412.13	378.03	409.47	375.62	408.23	374.49
2	415.04	379.55	410.31	369.72	403.26	375.99
3	408.81	370.82	397.48	371.21	410.79	369.54
% R.S.D	0.76	1.24	1.77	0.82	0.94	0.90

Table 22: Robustness data for Chlorthalidone drug

S. No.	Flow rate (-0.2 ml/minute) Area	Flow rate (0.2ml/minute) Area	pH (-0.2) Area	pH (+0.2) Area	Mobile phase (- 2) Area	Mobile phase (+2) Area
1	255.20	234.10	253.56	232.64	252.80	231.95
2	257.00	235.04	252.00	230.69	249.06	232.88
3	251.07	232.61	255.20	229.60	254.58	229.19
% R.S.D	1.20	0.52	0.63	0.67	1.12	0.83

Table 23: Robustness results for impurity-1

S. No.	Flow rate (-0.2 ml/minute) Area	Flow rate (0.2ml/minute) Area	pH (-0.2) Area	pH (+0.2) Area	Mobile phase (- 2) Area	Mobile phase (+2) Area
1	214.40	195.89	217.37	196.68	232.92	206.07
2	210.74	192.57	223.74	204.91	248.49	212.99
3	218.73	191.11	218.03	208.14	237.98	220.09
% R.S.D	1.86	1.27	1.59	2.91	3.31	3.29

Table 24: Robustness results for impurity-2

S. No.	Flow rate (-0.2 ml/minute) Area	Flow rate (0.2ml/minute) Area	pH (-0.2) Area	pH (+0.2) Area	Mobile phase (- 2) Area	Mobile phase (+2) Area
1	162.77	148.88	165.03	149.48	176.89	156.65
2	161.24	143.96	173.66	156.82	186.04	161.93
3	166.05	145.86	172.19	159.50	180.07	165.64
% R.S.D	1.50	1.70	2.71	3.34	2.57	2.80

Table 25: Analysis of available formulation (marketed) by developed and validated chromatography method

Impurity Estimation	
Impurity 1	0.32
Impurity 2	0.67
Unkown single maximum impurity	0.67
Total unknown impurities	1.04

9. Conclusion

The result of method validation proves that the proposed new methods for quantification of impurities in selected drugs are simple, sensitive, accurate, precise and robust in nature. The new developed methods are superior economical methods which can be conveniently adapted in quality control laboratories.

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